

SITE Sphinx	DATE 6/25/79	AREA NE	SQUARE N3/W1	PAGE
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Feature No.

Coordinates:		Levels	
		Top: 10.57	Bottom: ~ 10.52 Bottom Undulates
DIMENSIONS			
Diameter: 15 cm	Width:	Length:	Depth: 4-6 cms.

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions		
①	SAND	Brown-Grey	Packed	Med. Fine	T ○	Lm	Flecks, small Frag	Gp x Pink - small fleck
						Gr		Char
					D	Do		
						Ba		
						Al		
Other								
②	Gypsum	Yellow-white			T ○	Lm		Gp
						Gr		Char Flecks (minute)
					D	Do		
						Ba		
						Al		
Other								
○					T	Lm		Gp
						Gr		Char
					D	Do		
						Ba		
						Al		
Other								
○					T	Lm		Gp
						Gr		Char
					D	Do		
						Ba		
						Al		
Other								
○					T	Lm		Gp
						Gr		Char
					D	Do		
						Ba		
						Al		
Other								

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ CI No./ 26 27	B&W: Roll/ BWI No./ 21 22
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:20	Feature Plan: 1:2	Sections:
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: Shallow round cutting, Probably excavated NS '78, Removal ④, Filled, like surrounding depressions w gypsum - of which only traces (② Above) Remain